

Conclusion Old RBC transfusion increased plasma fHb in septic patients. Increasing plasma fHb levels after transfusion were associated with decreased microvascular density and lower increase in tissue Hb content. This relation might be blunted when the glycocalyx is preserved.

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Fatty acid composition of blood plasma in multiple organ dysfunction syndrome

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Introduction The aim of study was to assess the fatty acid (FA) composition of blood plasma in multiple organ dysfunction syndrome (MODS).

Methods The objects of the study were 18 people with multiple organ failure (35.6 ± 8.7 years) of various etiologies. The blood of 16 healthy volunteers aged 37.7 ± 3.2 years served as control. There were also analyzed blood plasma and fragments of artery luminal part from patients who died from different causes. Analysis of FA was conducted using capillary gas-liquid chromatography. Quantitative evaluation of individual FA content was made as a mass percentage of their total. Statistical analysis was performed using the Mann-Whitney U test ($P < 0.05$).

Results Normalized contents of oleic and palmitoleic monounsaturated FA increase in patients with MODS, while the levels of stearic saturated FA and polyunsaturated FA decrease, as compared with the control. Considering these results, we conclude that blood plasma FA composition in MODS biased towards composition of FA characteristic of adipose and muscle tissue triglycerides, which quantitatively predominant monounsaturated FA, and stearic and polyunsaturated FA have a significantly lower level [1,2]. Thus, the composition of the FA in MODS reflects the degree of lipolysis activation in fat depots. As a result of these processes there should occur an imbalance in vascular endothelial cells between monounsaturated and polyunsaturated FA and, as a consequence, changes in metabolism of eicosanoids and other lipid vasoactive mediators should develop. One should note that in plasma of people who died in a hospital environment due to various reasons, similar changes in FA blood composition are observed. The degree of change of FA composition in postmortem blood samples presumably primarily depends on severity and duration of a previous critical and serious condition. Postmortem changes presumably exert some influence on blood plasma FA composition. Moreover, the composition of FA in blood plasma in the case of MODS is similar to that of FA in the luminal part of the artery wall. This suggests a decrease in the influence of intertissue differences in lipid composition on metabolic processes.

Conclusion Given that the monounsaturated FAs in the case of MODS enter the bloodstream primarily from adipose and muscle tissues, one can assume that their blood plasma level reflects the degree of hypermetabolism processes in the organism.

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Response of coagulation and fibrinolysis system was different between older and nonolder patients with severe sepsis

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Introduction The present study investigated the relationship between age [1] and biomarkers of coagulation and fibrinolysis [2] and their impact on outcome in severe sepsis patients.

Methods A prospective observational study of adult patients with severe sepsis was conducted in a single academic hospital. Plasma was analyzed for coagulation and fibrinolysis markers on days 1, 2, and 3. Patients were stratified according to the age 67 years, which was the point of the Youden index (maximum sensitivity + specificity - 1) in a receiver operation characteristics plot for a logistic regression model of in-hospital mortality.

Results For the in-hospital survival rate, that of older sepsis patients was significantly lower than younger patients, 9/15 (60.0%) versus 27/28 (96.4%), $P < 0.05$. Older patients had markedly higher total plasmin activator inhibitor-1 (TPAI-1) on day 1, thrombin-antithrombin complex (TAT) on days 2 and 3, and fibrin monomer complex on day 2, and markedly lower plasminogen (PMG) on day 3 and alpha-plasmin inhibitor (α PI) on days 2 and 3 compared with younger patients (all $P < 0.05$). Age was an independent predictor of high TAT on days 2 and 3, high fibrin monomer complex on day 2, low PMG on day 3, and low α PI on days 2 and 3 after adjusting for some cofactors and covariables. TPAI-1 on day 2, TAT on day 2, and PMG on day 3 were risk factors of in-hospital mortality in older sepsis patients (Table 1).

Table 1 (abstract P103). Univariate analysis of logistic regression for in-hospital mortality

	HR	95% CI	P
PAI-1 day 2	1.02	1.0 to 1.06	<0.01
TAT day 2	1.49	1.02 to 1.9	<0.05
PMG day 3	0.64	0.1 to 0.95	<0.01
SOFA day 1	1.2	0.9 to 1.69	0.21
IL-6 day 1	0.99	0.9 to 1.00	0.21

Conclusion In severe sepsis, older patients displayed a biomarker profile suggestive of enhanced response of coagulation and fibrinolysis system compared with younger patients. Change of some markers depended on age and may contribute to the poor outcome in older patients.

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ϵ -Aminocaproic acid does not increase adverse effects in cardiac surgery: an analysis of 2,852 cases

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Introduction Antifibrinolytic drugs recently have been associated with adverse outcomes in patients undergoing cardiac surgery. We reviewed our experience with prophylactic ϵ -aminocaproic acid in patients undergoing cardiac surgery at InCor - Heart Institute.

Methods We retrieved data on 2,852 consecutive patients undergoing cardiac surgery at Duke between 1 January 2004 and 31 December 2008. We compared patients receiving or not prophylactic ϵ -aminocaproic acid in coronary artery bypass graft surgery, or valve procedures or combined ones. We evaluated baseline characteristics, intraoperative data and severe clinical endpoints during 30 days.

Results A total of 2,852 patients were included in the analysis and 1,389 (48.7%) received prophylactic ϵ -aminocaproic acid. The others did not receive any antifibrinolytic. In the risk-adjusted model, survival was similar among patients treated with aminocaproic acid or not treated (1.9 vs. 1.6%, $P = 0.48$). Bleeding in 24 hours was reduced in the treated group as compared with the nontreated (391 vs. 472 ml, $P = 0.012$). There were no differences regarding acute renal failure, stroke and infection in 30 days.